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The Influence of Social Media and Study Habit on Student Academic Performance

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the impact of social media usage and study habits on the academic performance of students at MSU-Balo-i Community High School during the Academic Year 2023-2024. A descriptive-correlational survey methodology was utilized to explore the connections between social media engagement, study habits, and academic achievement among Grade 7, 10, 11, and 12 students, with a focus on Facebook users, totaling three hundred (300) participants. The study delved into various dimensions of social media usage, including performance index, entertainment index, health influence, isolation index, social networking connections, and time consumption. On the other hand, study habits were assessed across eight sub-scales: time management, physical well-being, reading proficiency, note-taking skills, learning motivation, memory retention, exam preparation, and overall health awareness. The findings revealed that students generally held a positive self-assessment of their study habits across multiple dimensions. Moreover, the academic performance of the students was notably commendable, with a majority demonstrating excellence. However, divergent viewpoints emerged regarding the impact of social media, with many students expressing concerns about its potential negative effects on academic performance. While the study did not find a mediating role for study habits in the relationship between social media use and academic performance, the results underscore the importance of addressing students' perceptions and behaviors concerning social media to optimize their academic outcomes. Future interventions could focus on promoting balanced social media usage while enhancing effective study habits to support students in achieving their academic goals.

Keywords: *social media, study habit, academic performance*

Introduction

In today's interconnected world, social media has become a ubiquitous means of communication, transcending geographical boundaries and bridging the gaps between different generations. The Asian region, in particular, has witnessed an exponential surge in social network site (SNS) usage among teenagers, making it a focal point of research on its impact on academic performance. Studies have shown that excessive social media usage can impede students' study time and divert their attention from academic responsibilities, leading to concerns about its potential influence on learners' educational outcomes (Burr et al., 2020).

While some research suggests that social media use for academic purposes may not significantly affect academic performance as measured by cumulative grade point average, the picture changes when it comes to utilizing social media for non-academic purposes and engaging in social media multitasking, which has shown to have significant negative correlations with academic performance (Law, 2017).

Considering social media's widespread usage, it has evolved into a vital platform for people of all ages, providing a channel for information sharing, communication, and entertainment on a global scale. The youth, in particular, have embraced social media as a pastime activity, accessible anytime and anywhere there is an internet connection. Consequently, the dynamics of social interaction have transformed, with social media becoming one of the primary sources of news and information for today's young generation.

However, academic performance remains a crucial aspect of a learner's life, with report cards and assessment results reflecting their progress and performance in academic tasks assigned by teachers. Therefore, it is imperative to understand the relationship between social media usage and study habits, which refer to learners' ability to effectively manage time and resources to accomplish academic tasks (Tus et al., 2020).

Study habits become ingrained routines that individuals adopt to enhance their learning process (Kaur, & Singh, 2020). In light of these considerations, the current study seeks to investigate the effects of social media on the study habits of students in the Mindanao State University-Balo-i Community High School, Balo-i Lanao Del Norte, Philippines. By contextualizing these issues within the local setting, this research aims to shed light on the existing problems and challenges faced by learners in this specific region, offering valuable insights for educational stakeholders and policymakers. It aimed to determine if this age of digital technology, especially the youth who have become fully involved in social networking all the time, also to investigate the influence of this on their study habits and, consequently, their academic performance.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effects of social media and study habits on the academic performance of students. Further, this aimed to investigate the mediating effect of study habits on the relationship between social media and the academic performance of the students. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following problems:

1. How do the respondents assess social media use relative to:
 - 1.1 performance index;
 - 1.2 entertainment index;
 - 1.3 health influence;
 - 1.4 isolation index;
 - 1.5 social network connections; and
 - 1.6 consuming time index?
2. How do the respondents assess their study habits relative to:
 - 2.1 budgeting time;
 - 2.2 physical condition;
 - 2.3 reading ability;
 - 2.4 note-taking;
 - 2.5 learning motivation;
 - 2.6 memory; and
 - 2.7 taking examinations?
3. What is the academic performance of the respondents during the school year 2022-2023?
4. Do the social media usage and benefits predict the academic performance of the respondents?
5. Do the study habits predict the academic performance of the respondents?
6. Do study habits mediate the relationship between social media usage and the academic performance of the respondents?
7. What action plan can be formulated based on the findings of the study?

Methodology

This section presents the different research components that are used in the study. This includes the discussion of the research design, research environment, subject of the study/respondents, sampling design instruments used and validity, gathering procedure, and statistical tools used in the research.

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive-correlational survey research design which uses survey questionnaires to gather data to determine the relationship and influence of social media and study habits on student's academic performance. The independent variable in this study is social media usage like Facebook, which includes various dimensions such as performance index, entertainment index, health influence, isolation index, social networking connections, and consuming time index. Through the descriptive-correlational analysis, the researcher aims to explore how these different aspects of social media usage are related to each other and how they relate to study habits and academic performance.

The mediating variable in this study is the study habits of the respondents, which includes factors such as time management, physical condition, reading ability, note-taking, learning motivation, memory, taking examinations, and health. The descriptive-correlational analysis helped the researcher understand the relationships between these study habits and how they might be associated with different aspects of social media usage and academic performance.

The dependent variable in this study was the academic performance of the respondents. Through the descriptive-correlational method, the researcher examined the relationships between academic performance and social media usage as well as academic performance and study habits.

Then, the study incorporates mediation analysis to test the mediating effect of study habits on the relationship between social media usage and academic performance. Mediation analysis allowed the researcher to explore whether study habits play a significant role in explaining how social media usage influences academic performance. By conducting mediation analysis, the study aimed to provide insights into the mechanisms through which social media impacts academic performance, with study habits acting as a potential mediating factor.

Participants

The respondents of this study were the high school (junior and senior) students who were enrolled in MSU-Balo-i Community High School this academic year 2023-2024. The focus of the research was to explore the relationships between social media usage, study habits, and academic performance, the participation of students was crucial, as they were the primary subjects affected by these variables in the educational setting.

Using the Raosoft sample size calculator, out of 1346 students in the population, 300 is the minimum recommended sample size of respondents that part of this study. with the critical value for the 95% confidence level, $z=1.96$, margin of error, $e=0.05$, and proportion, $p=0.50$. Thus, the researcher decided on a sample size of 300 which is above the recommended minimum requirement, with a margin of error of 5% at the 95% confidence interval.

Preliminary profiling analysis showed that an overwhelming 98% of the participants were active members of various social networking sites, with a majority predominantly using Facebook, trailed by Instagram and other social media platforms. Their engagement with these platforms primarily revolves around activities such as conducting research, establishing connections, staying updated on trends, engaging in blogging, and participating in online gaming.

The sampling procedure employed in this study was the simple random sampling method. Simple random sampling is a probability sampling technique where every individual in the population has an equal chance of being selected as a participant in the study. It ensures that each member of the population has an unbiased and independent chance of being included in the sample, thus enhancing the generalizability of the study's findings to the larger population.

In the context of the current study, simple random sampling entails randomly selected students from the entire student population of MSU-BCHS, without any specific criteria or restrictions, to be part of the research. This process ensures that all students have an equal likelihood of being chosen to participate, reducing the risk of potential biases in the sample selection.

To apply simple random sampling, the researcher can use various methods, such as using a random number generator or drawing names from a hat. Each student's name in the student population was assigned a unique number or identifier, and a random selection process was employed to determine the participants. This random selection process ensured that the sample represented the diversity and characteristics of the entire student population, making it more likely to yield reliable and generalizable results.

By utilizing simple random sampling, the study can have obtained a representative sample of students from MSU-BCHS, allowing for more robust and valid conclusions about the relationships between social media usage, study habits, and academic performance among the student body. It ensured that the findings of the study could be applied to a broader population beyond the specific group of respondents, increasing the study's external validity and relevance.

Instruments

To gather the data, the instrument utilized in this study consisted of an adopted questionnaire derived from the works of Abu-Shanab et al. (2015) and Tus et al. (2020). This questionnaire was structured into three distinct parts. The first part aimed to ascertain the respondents' level of engagement with social media platforms about various factors, including performance index, entertainment index, health influence, isolation index, SN (Social Network) connections, and time spent on social media. Abu-Shanab et al. (2015) demonstrated the reliability of this instrument, achieving a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.888 for the 18 items.

Moving on to Part II, this segment focused on the respondents' perceptions regarding their study habits. They were asked to indicate their frequency of engaging in certain study habits by selecting one of the options: Always, Often, Sometimes, and Never. The instrument utilized for this section was the Palsane and Sharma Study Habits Inventory (PSSHI), developed by M.N. Palsane and Saddhna Sharma. A higher score in this section indicated a stronger adherence to effective study habits. The reliability of the PSSHI was assessed using both the test-retest method and the split-half technique, yielding reliability coefficients of 0.88 and 0.56, respectively.

Finally, Part III of the questionnaire captured the academic performance of the respondents during the academic year 2022-2023. By employing this adapted questionnaire, the study aims to comprehensively investigate the relationship between social media usage, study habits, and academic performance among the respondents. The instrument's reliability, as established through previous research, bolstered its suitability for data collection and analysis in the context of this current study.

Procedure

In the data-gathering procedure, the finalized questionnaires were distributed among the respondents after obtaining their informed consent. Before the administration of the survey, the researcher provided the participants with an informed consent form to explain the purpose and nature of the survey. The form outlined the voluntary nature of participation and the right to withdraw from the study at any time without repercussions. The respondents were informed about the confidentiality and anonymity of their responses, ensuring that their personal information remains protected.

Upon receiving the informed consent from the students, the researcher proceeded to explain the content of the questionnaire and the process of how to accomplish it. The duration of administering the survey was one day, during which the researcher was available to address any queries or clarifications that the respondents may have while completing the questionnaires.

During this process, the participants were encouraged to provide honest and thoughtful responses, understanding that their participation was crucial for the success of the study. Once the survey period was completed, the researcher collected all the filled questionnaires, ensuring that the participants' identities remained confidential.

The researcher made a letter and sought approval from the school principal and Registrar in Charge to ask permission to get the Academic performance of the respondents during the school year 2022-2023.

Subsequently, the researcher organized and analyzed the data, adhering to ethical guidelines and data protection measures. The responses were coded and entered into statistical analysis software for a thorough examination. Descriptive statistics and correlational

analyses were conducted to identify patterns and relationships between the variables. Additionally, mediation analysis was employed to explore the potential mediating effect of study habits on the relationship between social media usage and academic performance. The findings were carefully interpreted and presented in a comprehensive report, outlining the research's outcomes and implications while upholding the confidentiality and privacy of the participants' information.

By incorporating the informed consent form in the data-gathering procedure, the research ensured that the rights and welfare of the participants were safeguarded, and the study was conducted ethically and responsibly. The insights derived from this data-gathering procedure, in conjunction with the informed consent obtained, contributed to a deeper understanding of the dynamics between social media, study habits, and academic performance among MSU-BCHS students in the academic year 2023-2024.

Statistical Treatment

After the respondents finished answering the survey, the researcher gathered and tabulated the results of the survey. Then, the researcher summarized and analyzed the data using various statistical tools to gain meaningful insights into the relationships between social media usage, study habits, and academic performance among MSU-BCHS students.

To describe the respondents' perspectives on social media, study habits, and academic performance (Problems 1, 2, and 3), the researcher used the mean and standard deviation. The mean provided the average score of the respondents' perceptions, while the standard deviation indicated the extent of variation or dispersion in the data. These statistics helped in understanding the central tendency and the spread of responses, enabling the researcher to assess the overall level of engagement with social media, study habits, and academic performance among the students.

For Problems 4 and 5, the researcher employed Ordinal Logistic Regression, and Multiple Linear Regression analysis was used to test if social media usage and benefits significantly predict the academic performance of the respondents. Multiple linear regression was used to determine the effect of study habits on their academic performance.

In Problem 6, the researcher utilized regression analysis with mediation analysis to investigate the mediating effect of study habits on the relationship between social media usage and academic performance. Regression analysis helped in understanding the predictive relationship between variables, and in this case, it examined how study habits may have influenced the association between social media usage and academic performance.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results, analysis, discussion, and interpretation of the data gathered by the researcher.

Problem 1: How do the respondents assess social media use relative to the performance index, entertainment index, health influence, isolation index, social network connections, and consuming time index?

It can be seen in Table 1 presents the respondents' assessment of social media use relative to the performance index. The mean and standard deviation (SD) values provide insights into the central tendency and variability of the responses.

Table 1. Respondents' Assessment of Social Media Use Relative to Performance Index

Indicators*	Mean	SD	Description
1. I neglect my assignments to spend more time on the Internet.	2.90	0.72	Sometimes
2. My academic performance declined because of using Facebook.	3.30	0.72	Sometimes
3. My Facebook use negatively influenced my academic performance.	3.17	0.81	Sometimes
4. My use of Facebook is causing me to abandon my studies.	3.23	0.85	Sometimes
5. My use of Facebook is causing me to neglect my academic duties.	3.24	0.83	Sometimes
Total Measure	3.17	0.49	Sometimes

Note: 1.00-1.49 Always 2.50-3.49 Sometimes*-reverse scoring 1.50-2.49 Often 3.50-4.00 Never

The overall mean of 3.17 (SD=0.49) indicates that respondents generally agreed to a modest extent with statements showing the detrimental effects of social media use on academic achievement. Individual responses revealed that they occasionally put off doing their homework in favor of spending more time online (Mean=2.90, SD=0.72) and that their use of Facebook has a negative impact on their academic performance (Mean=3.30, SD=0.72). Additionally, respondents acknowledged that their Facebook use sometimes influences their academic performance negatively (Mean=3.17, SD=0.81) and may lead to abandoning studies (Mean=3.23, SD=0.85) or neglecting academic duties (Mean = 3.24, SD = 0.83).

These results indicated a significant pattern among participants, suggesting a possible relationship between social media use and academic achievement. The mean values, which are close to the middle of the scale, show that respondents are not entirely in agreement or disagreement with the detrimental effects of social media on their academic obligations. A degree of consistency in the responses is shown by the comparatively low standard deviations, which point to an agreement among the respondents.

Implications of these results may highlight the need for educational institutions and students alike to be conscious of the potential distractions posed by social media platforms. While the moderate agreement suggests that the negative impact is not universal, it is

still a significant concern that warrants attention. Teachers should think about including time management and digital literacy in their curricula to assist students in finding a balance between their academic obligations and their online interests. Reisdorf et al. (2020) claimed that there are more drawbacks than benefits to academics using social media. Social media has a negative effect on students' academic achievement. Higher education students are more likely to be addicted to social media, which undermines their ability to perform academically (Nalwa & Anand, 2003).

Table 2. Respondents' Assessment of Social Media Use Relative to Entertainment

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. I find that I spent more time than I intended on Facebook.	2.51	0.78	Often
2. I feel excited and thrilled when using Facebook.	2.22	0.83	Sometimes
3. Life without Facebook is boring and empty of joy.	2.27	0.95	Sometimes
4. I engage in social interactions, such as chatting and commenting, while using Facebook	2.77	0.97	Often
5. I prioritize using Facebook over engaging in other offline leisure activities.	2.13	0.86	Sometimes
Total Measure	2.38	0.52	Sometimes

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never 2.50-3.49 Often 1.50-2.49 Sometimes 3.50-4.00 Always

Table 2 shows the respondents' assessment of social media use for entertainment, with indicators assessing various aspects of their interactions with Facebook. On average, respondents reported a a modest degree of agreement with statements reflecting the entertainment value of Facebook, as indicated by the overall mean of 2.38 (SD=0.52). Individual respondents stated that they frequently discover themselves using Facebook for longer periods of time than they had planned (Mean = 2.51, SD = 0.78) and for social contacts (Mean = 2.77, SD = 0.97). The respondents also said that they occasionally prioritize using Facebook over other offline leisure activities (Mean=2.13, SD=0.86), feel excited and thrilled when using Facebook (Mean=2.22, SD=0.83), and think life would be boring and devoid of joy without Facebook (Mean=2.27, SD=0.95).

These findings revealed that, generally speaking, respondents think of Facebook as a source of excitement and amusement; moderate mean values reflect a rather balanced viewpoint. Although not incredibly low, the standard deviations point to some degree of consistency in the responses, suggesting a common opinion among the participants.

The ramifications of these results centered on the respondents' use of social media—especially Facebook—as a source of amusement. The respondents' frequent participation in social contacts on the site suggests that the entertainment component does not play a major role in their leisure time, despite the moderate agreement suggesting otherwise. Teachers and legislators should think about recognizing social media's entertainment value and investigating methods to use it to encourage positive participation. Some ideas include integrating social media into lessons or encouraging appropriate online socialization.

According to Kirschner and Karpinski's (2010) study, Facebook was determined to be the main source of distraction for students, however this finding revealed no difference. Some research, however, present different conclusions and contend that kids gain from talking since it increases their vocabulary and writing abilities (Kolan & Dzandza, 2018).

The respondents' evaluation of social media use's impact on health is displayed in Table 3, which includes both good and negative indications related to their online experiences. With an overall mean score of 2.26 (SD = 0.54), respondents generally expressed a considerable degree of concurrence with statements highlighting the negative effects of social media use on health.

Table 3. Respondents' Assessment of Social Media Use Relative to Health Influence

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. I am depressed and nervous when I am forbidden from using the net.	1.87	0.86	Sometimes
2. I suffer from eye strain because of using the net.	2.20	0.98	Sometimes
3. I often "like", "share", or "comment" on health-related posts or articles on social media.	2.34	0.93	Sometimes
4. I follow or subscribe to social media accounts of health and wellness influencers.	2.50	0.93	Often
5. I receive social support and encouragement from my online social network regarding my health and fitness goals.	2.39	0.94	Sometimes
Total Measure	2.26	0.54	Sometimes

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never 2.50-3.49 Often 1.50-2.49 Sometimes 3.50-4.00 Always

Individually, respondents indicated that they sometimes experience depressive sensations and nervousness when forbidden from using the internet (Mean=1.87, SD=0.86) and occasionally experience eye strain due to internet use (Mean=2.20, SD=0.98). On a more positive note, respondents often engage with health-related content on social media by "liking," "sharing," or "commenting" on posts or articles (Mean=2.34, SD=0.93), subscribing to accounts of health and wellness influencers (Mean=2.50, SD=0.93), and occasionally receiving social support and encouragement from their online social network regarding health and fitness goals (Mean=2.39, SD=0.94).

These results suggest a nuanced the link between health and social media use influence among respondents. While there are instances of negative experiences such as feelings of depression and eye strain, the overall mean indicates a moderate level of agreement, reflecting a balanced perspective. The standard deviations suggest a degree of variability in responses, indicating that individuals have diverse experiences with the health influence of social media.

The implications of these findings underscored the dual nature of social media's influence on health. Educators, health professionals,

and individuals alike may benefit from recognizing both the potential negative consequences, such as mental health challenges and physical strain, and the positive aspects, like having access to health-related information and social support. Health and wellness campaigns could leverage social media platforms to disseminate accurate information and encourage positive health behaviors. Individuals may benefit from developing strategies for mindful internet use to mitigate negative health effects while maximizing the positive aspects. Good websites, like Facebook, can't always be considered good because of the terrible and worse uses that some people make of them, such as cyberbullying and other suitable actions. We have observed a decline in our attention spans in recent years since the introduction of the internet and social networking sites in particular (Gerald, 2011).

Table 4. Respondents' Assessment of Social Media Use Relative to Isolation

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. I refuse to spend time on family activities to stay on Facebook.	1.45	0.68	Never
2. I am disconnected from my friends because of using Facebook.	1.60	0.78	Sometimes
3. My use of Facebook and the net causes isolation from my world	1.88	0.84	Sometimes
4. I feel isolated or lonely after spending time on social media.	2.19	0.98	Sometimes
5. I've noticed a decrease in my face-to-face social interactions as a result of spending more time on social media.	2.23	0.92	Sometimes
Total Measure	1.87	0.52	Sometimes

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never 2.50-3.49 Often 1.50-2.49 Sometimes 3.50-4.00 Always

Table 4 displays the respondents' assessment of usage of social media about isolation, with indicators covering various aspects of social interactions and connection. On average, respondents reported a moderate level of agreement with statements reflecting the potential isolation resulting from utilizing social media, with an overall mean of 1.87 (SD=0.52). Individual respondents said they almost never say no to family time in order to continue using Facebook (Mean=1.45, SD=0.68). However, they sometimes feel disconnected from friends due to Facebook use (Mean=1.60, SD=0.78), experience isolation from their world because of Facebook and online resources (Mean=1.88, SD=0.84), feel isolated or lonely after spending time on social media (Mean=2.19, SD=0.98), and notice a decrease in face-to-face social interactions due to spending more time on social media (Mean=2.23, SD=0.92).

These findings revealed a connection between respondents' sense of isolation and their use of social media. Although there are some situations in which social media use can exacerbate feelings of isolation and detachment, the overall mean shows a moderate degree of agreement, indicating a well-rounded viewpoint. The standard deviations point to some degree of response variability, suggesting that people's experiences with the social ramifications of social media use vary widely.

The implications of these findings emphasized the potential social consequences of excessive social media use. Although the average results show a moderate degree of agreement, the responses' wide range implies that some people might be more prone to isolation than others. The promotion of positive social media behaviors and the significance of striking a balance between online and offline social connections could be the main goals of educational initiatives and interventions. Self-awareness programs that promote social media usage with mindfulness and provoke contemplation about how digital interactions affect in-person relationships may be beneficial to individuals.

Accordingly, Burke et al. (2009) concluded that overall social networking site activities are favorably connected to bonding and bridging social capital. It is also negatively associated with loneliness. Other studies found a negative relationship between Internet use and face-to-face interaction (Bruni & Stanca, 2008; Frey et al., 2007; Robinson & Martin, 2008). Internet use may interfere with communication at home, where family members devote more attention to computers than with each other. Research indicated that weaker relations generated online were substituting stronger offline relations with family and friends. These days, using the Internet is closely associated with having access to social networking sites, which encourages social interaction.

Table 5. Respondents' Assessment of Social Media Use Relative to Social Network Connection

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. I am looking to make more friends on Facebook	2.60	0.99	Often
2. I feel relieved because of my relationship on Facebook.	2.23	0.87	Sometimes
3. I have a large number of online friends or connections on my social networking profiles.	2.33	0.98	Sometimes
4. I engage in conversations and interactions with my online friends or connections.	2.62	0.88	Often
5. My online connections represent a diverse range of people from different backgrounds and locations.	2.30	0.82	Sometimes
Total Measure	2.41	0.62	Sometimes

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never 2.50-3.49 Often 1.50-2.49 Sometimes 3.50-4.00 Always

The evaluations of social media use for social network connection, including friend-making, relief-related emotions, the quantity of online connections, and the variety of online networks, are shown in Table 5. The overall mean of 2.41 (SD=0.62) indicates that respondents generally reported a moderate level of agreement with statements indicating the social network connection aspect of social media use. Individually, respondents expressed a tendency to actively seek new friends on Facebook (Mean=2.60, SD=0.99) and often engage in conversations and interactions with online friends or connections (Mean=2.62, SD=0.88).

Additionally, they sometimes feel comforted because of their relationships on Facebook (Mean=2.23, SD=0.87) and have a moderate number of online friends or connections on their social networking profiles (Mean=2.33, SD=0.98). Respondents also indicated that

their online connections sometimes represent a wide variety of people from different backgrounds and locations (Mean=2.30, SD=0.82).

These results disclosed that the respondents view social media as a platform that facilitates social network connections, both concerning of quantity and diversity. The moderate mean values indicate a balanced perspective, while the standard deviations suggest a degree of variability in responses, indicating that individuals have diverse experiences with the social connection element of social media.

The implications of these findings highlighted the positive social aspects of social media utilization, particularly in terms of connection-building and the potential for diverse online networks. Educators and researchers may consider exploring ways to leverage social media to foster positive social connections and promote inclusivity. Individuals could benefit from strategies that enhance the quality and diversity of their online social networks while being mindful of the potential for online interactions to complement, rather than substitute, face-to-face relationships.

Because of the COVID-19 pandemic, massive open online courses, or MOOCs, have gained popularity since 2020 (Raja & Kallarakal, 2020). MOOC courses are open to all online students and are typically free. Many well-known universities offer their online courses on MOOCs platforms, giving students flexible options for learning. Students find them helpful in developing their careers as well as expanding their knowledge base. In partnership with the MOOC platform, numerous independent colleges have incorporated these courses into their curricula (Chen, 2013).

Table 6 outlines respondents' assessments of social media use about a consuming time index, covering aspects such as daily hours devoted to Facebook, late-night internet use, disclosure of online time to family, overall screen time, and the balance between leisure and productive activities.

Table 6. Respondents' Assessment of Social Media Use Relative to Consuming Time Index

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. I spend long hours daily on Facebook.	2.16	0.85	Sometimes
2. I stay late at night when using the Internet and Facebook.	2.30	0.97	Sometimes
3. I don't tell my family the exact hours I spent on Facebook.	2.45	1.10	Sometimes
4. I spend a significant amount of time each day using screens (e.g. TV, computer, smartphone).	2.50	0.91	Often
5. I find that I spend more time on leisure or recreational activities than on productive or work-related tasks.	2.29	0.74	Sometimes
Total Measure	2.34	0.61	Sometimes

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never 2.50-3.49 Often 1.50-2.49 Sometimes 3.50-4.00 Always

Table 6 outlines respondents' assessments of social media use about a consuming time index, covering aspects such as daily hours spent on Facebook, late-night internet use, disclosure of online time to family, overall screen time, and the balance between leisure and productive activities.

With an overall mean score of 2.34 (SD=0.61), respondents generally expressed a modest degree of consensus with statements highlighting the time-consuming component of using social media. Individual respondents reported that they frequently spend a significant amount of time using screens each day (Mean=2.50, SD=0.91), occasionally find themselves spending more time on leisure or recreational activities than on productive or work-related tasks (Mean=2.29, SD=0.74), and occasionally spend long hours on Facebook every day (Mean=2.16, SD=0.85), stay up late at night using the internet and Facebook (Mean=2.30, SD=0.97).

These results displayed that the respondents acknowledge the potential time-consuming nature of social media use. The moderate mean values indicate a balanced perspective, while the standard deviations suggest a degree of variability in responses, indicating that individuals have diverse experiences with the time-related aspects of social media.

The implications of these findings emphasized the need for individuals to be mindful of their online activities and amount of time on social media. Educational programs and interventions could focus on promoting healthy screen time habits and time management skills. Additionally, individuals may benefit from strategies that assist in finding a balance between productive duties and pleasure pastimes on the internet. Awareness campaigns and educational initiatives could encourage open communication within families regarding online activities, fostering a nurturing setting for responsible technology use. Overall, the results underscore the importance of promoting a balanced approach to social media use that aligns with overall well-being and productivity.

Another researcher, Tynes (2009), affirmed that parents are extremely concerned about their teenagers' compulsive usage of social media, which causes them to neglect their schoolwork. Even though there are stringent regulations on the usage of these technological devices set by various school authorities, he noticed that even schools and society at large are becoming concerned. According to complaints made by Abdullah et al. (2009) and Lent et al. (2009), a lot of children lose the social graces necessary to treat their parents and professors with the respect they deserve after spending so much time on social media and its influences.

Table 7 provides a comprehensive summary of respondents' assessments of social media use across multiple dimensions, including the Performance Index, Entertainment, Health Influence, Isolation, Social Network Connection, and Consuming Time Index. The performance index revealed that respondents frequently believe social media use has a detrimental effect on academic performance, with a mean score of 3.17 (SD=0.49). With a mean score of 2.38 (SD=0.52) on the entertainment dimension, social media is

occasionally seen as a source of amusement. The mean of 2.26 (SD=0.54) for health influence showed a considerable degree of agreement with both the good and bad aspects of social media use for health. With a mean score of 1.87 (SD=0.52), the isolation dimension indicated that social media use may occasionally cause respondents to feel disconnected or alone. Regarding the social elements of using social media, there was a moderate degree of agreement indicated by the social network connection dimension, which had a mean of 2.41 (SD=0.62). Last but not least, the spending time index revealed that occasionally, respondents acknowledged the potentially time-consuming nature of using social media, with a mean of 2.34 (SD=0.61).

Table 7. *Consolidated Findings of the Respondents' Assessment of Social Media Use*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Performance Index	3.17	0.49	Often
Entertainment	2.38	0.52	Sometimes
Health Influence	2.26	0.54	Sometimes
Isolation	1.87	0.52	Sometimes
Social Network Connection	2.41	0.62	Sometimes
Consuming Time Index	2.34	0.61	Sometimes
Total Measure	2.41	0.30	Sometimes

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never 2.50-3.49 Often 1.50-2.49 Sometimes 3.50-4.00 Always

The overall score showed a moderate degree of agreement with the various features of social media use, with a mean of 2.41 (SD=0.30) that summarized respondents' views across all categories. There was some degree of unanimity among respondents, as indicated by the standard deviation for the total measure, which indicated a relatively low variability in responses.

These consolidated findings highlighted the multifaceted nature of individuals' experiences with social media, encompassing both positive and negative dimensions. A degree of consistency in respondents' overall ratings is indicated by the relatively low standard deviation for the whole measure, while the moderate averages across categories point to a nuanced and balanced viewpoint. The results highlight the significance of taking into account the various effects of social media on social, academic, and personal spheres. They also highlight the necessity of focused interventions and educational programs that address the unique advantages and disadvantages of social media use.

Students use social media's many applications on a daily basis to the point where it becomes a part of their lives, according to Al-Rahmi et al (2017). Their primary uses for these applications are educational and entertainment.

Problem 2: How do the respondents assess their study habits relative to budgeting time, physical condition, reading ability, note-taking, learning motivation, memory, and taking examinations?

Table 8 shows respondents' self-assessment of their study habits relative to budgeting time, covering various aspects such as daily study frequency, studying at specific times, completion of homework, incorporating breaks during longer study sessions, and dividing time-based on question requirements.

On average, respondents reported a positive assessment of their study habits concerning budgeting time, as indicated by the overall mean of 3.01 (SD=0.54). Individually, respondents reported studying every day (Mean=2.91, SD=0.78) and at specific times of the day (Mean=2.98, SD=0.79). They also indicated a regular completion of homework (Mean=3.07, SD=0.85) and frequent breaks during longer study sessions (Mean=3.12, SD=0.80). Additionally, respondents reported dividing their time based on the content to be answered about the number of questions (Mean=2.96, SD=0.85).

These results suggested that, on average, respondents exhibited positive study habits and effective time management strategies. The overall mean values, leaning towards the higher end of the scale, indicate a consistent and positive self-assessment. The standard deviations suggest a degree of variability in responses, reflecting individual differences in study habits.

Table 8. *Respondents' Assessment of Their Study Habits Relative to Budgeting Time*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. I study every day.	2.91	0.78	Often
2. I study at a particular time of the day.	2.98	0.79	Often
3. I do my homework daily.	3.07	0.85	Often
4. If I have to study for a longer time, I take a rest in between.	3.12	0.80	Often
5. I divide the time according to the matter to be answered in respect of the number of questions.	2.96	0.85	Often
Total Measure	3.01	0.54	Often

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never 2.50-3.49 Often 1.50-2.49 Sometimes 3.50-4.00 Always

The results of this study have important implications for how important it is to help students develop effective learning habits and time management skills. Teachers and educational institutions should think about implementing techniques that support the productive study habits mentioned in the responses. Some of these include highlighting consistent study schedules, recommending breaks during extended study sessions, and encouraging time management according to the requirements of the assignments. Programs that help students become more self-aware and reflect on their study habits as well as create customized time management plans could be beneficial.

The study supported Choney's (2010) claim that professors and economists are wondering if students' grades won't be impacted by how much time they spend on social media sites because of their popularity. Mehmood and Taswir (2013) provided additional support for this claim, stating that one of the most significant elements that can either positively or negatively impact students' academic performance is their usage of technology, such as the Internet. One of the abilities that affects students' academic achievement is time management, citing the research of Khanam, Sahu, Rao, Kar, and Quazi (2017).

Table 9. Respondents' Assessment of Their Study Habits Relative to Physical Condition

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. I have all the required books and other relevant materials for study with me.	2.51	0.84	Often
2. For the time of the study, I was disturbed by the surroundings at the time of the study.	2.76	0.92	Often
3. I develop an automatic interest in the subject as soon as I start studying it.	3.04	0.88	Often
4. I realize the importance of the subjects for my future career.	3.35	0.79	Often
5. Other stray thoughts gradually flow in as soon as I settle down for the study.	2.79	0.84	Often
6. I think that I can improve my study habits fairly.	3.22	0.78	Often
Total Measure	2.95	0.48	Often

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never 2.50-3.49 Often 1.50-2.49 Sometimes 3.50-4.00 Always

Table 9 presents respondents' self-assessment of their study practices relative to their physical condition, encompassing aspects such as having the required study materials, the impact of surroundings on study sessions, developing interest in subjects, realizing the significance of subjects for a future career, the occurrence of stray thoughts during the study, and the belief in the potential for improvement in study habits.

On average, respondents reported a positive assessment of their study habits concerning physical condition, as indicated by the overall mean of 2.95 (SD = 0.48). Individually, respondents reported often having each of the necessary books and study materials (Mean=2.51, SD=0.84), often getting disturbed by their surroundings during study sessions (Mean=2.76, SD=0.92), frequently developing automatic interest in subjects while studying (Mean=3.04, SD=0.88), often understanding the significance of subjects for their future careers (Mean=3.35, SD=0.79), experiencing stray thoughts during study sessions (Mean=2.79, SD=0.84), and often believing in the potential for improvement in their study habits (Mean=3.22, SD=0.78).

According to these findings, the respondents saw their study habits and physical health in an overall positive light. The overall mean values, leaning towards the higher end of the scale, indicate a consistent and positive evaluation. The standard deviations suggest a degree of variability in responses, reflecting individual differences in study habits.

The implications of these findings underscored the importance of considering the physical context and mindset in fostering effective study habits. Educational institutions and educators may consider strategies to minimize environmental disturbances during study sessions and promote the recognition of the significance of academic subjects for future career development. Additionally, interventions focusing on enhancing automatic interest in subjects and managing stray thoughts during study sessions may contribute to further improvement in study habits. The overall positive self-assessment provides a foundation for recognizing and building on existing strengths in study practices among respondents.

In actuality, Liftoff (2016) asserts that students' experiences in the classroom have an impact on them as well. Additionally, data demonstrates that when kids learn in a constructive way and fully engage their minds, they study more effectively.

Table 10 outlines respondents' self-assessment of their study habits relative to reading ability, covering various aspects such as pre-reading main points, perseverance in reading despite difficulties, careful reading for understanding, silent reading habits, adjusting reading speed based on importance and difficulty, thorough examination of figures and graphs, reading books during free time, and regular library usage.

On average, respondents reported a positive assessment of their study habits concerning reading ability, as indicated by the overall mean of 2.79 (SD=0.44). Individually, respondents reported often reading main points before delving into chapters (Mean=3.22, SD=0.83), often continuing to read despite difficulties in understanding some words (Mean=3.11, SD=0.86), often reading very carefully to understand every point (Mean=3.39, SD=0.79), sometimes reading silently (Mean=2.35, SD=0.99), often adjusting reading speed based on importance and difficulty (Mean=2.95, SD=0.84), often studying figures and graphs carefully while reading (Mean=2.99, SD=0.85), often reading books during free time (Mean=2.58, SD=0.99), and sometimes studying frequently in the library (Mean=1.74, SD=0.84).

These results confirmed that the respondents exhibited positive self-assessments of their study habits related to reading ability. The overall mean values, leaning towards the higher end of the scale, indicate a consistent and positive evaluation. The standard deviations suggest a degree of variability in responses, reflecting individual differences in study habits.

The implications of these findings highlighted the importance of effective reading strategies in fostering positive study habits. Academic institutions and instructors should think about supporting and encouraging reading strategies include skimming the essential ideas, reading slowly, and modifying reading pace according to the level of the material. In addition, interventions could focus on encouraging regular library usage, as it was identified as a less frequently practiced habit among respondents. The positive self-

assessment provides valuable insights into the strengths of respondents' study habits related to reading ability. This comprehension of reading proficiency is important since it helps pupils advance. Chuks, Subair, and Chima (2017) assert that reading is important for students' academic achievement and plays a critical role in the lives of understudies. It will help them transform into lifelong learners.

Table 10. *Respondents' Assessment of Their Study Habits Relative to Reading Ability*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. I read the main points before I read the chapter.	3.22	0.83	Often
2. I continue my reading despite the difficulties in understanding the meaning of some words.	3.11	0.86	Often
3. I read very carefully in order to understand every point.	3.39	0.79	Often
4. I never read silently	2.35	0.99	Sometimes
5. According to the importance and difficulty of the subject matter, I change and adjust the speed of my reading.	2.95	0.84	Often
6. I study figures and graphs very carefully while reading.	2.99	0.85	Often
7. I read books whenever I have free time, whether at home or in school/College.	2.58	0.99	Often
8. I study in the library regularly.	1.74	0.84	Sometimes
Total Measure	2.79	0.44	Often

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never 2.50-3.49 Often 1.50-2.49 Sometimes 3.50-4.00 Always

Table 11. *Respondents' Assessment of Their Study Habits Relative to Note-Taking*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. I take down notes while reading.	2.82	0.97	Often
2. During classroom teaching, I take down notes very sincerely.	3.18	0.87	Often
3. At home, I compare my class notes with the notes from the textbooks.	2.63	0.99	Often
Total Measure	2.88	0.71	Often

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never 2.50-3.49 Often 1.50-2.49 Sometimes 3.50-4.00 Always

Table 11 presents respondents' self-assessment of their study habits relative to note-taking, covering aspects such as taking notes while reading, taking notes during classroom teaching, and comparing class notes with textbook notes. On average, respondents reported a positive assessment of their study habits concerning notetaking, as indicated by the overall mean of 2.88 (SD=0.71). According to the individual responses, participants frequently took notes when reading (Mean=2.82, SD=0.97), frequently took earnest notes during instruction in the classroom (Mean=3.18, SD=0.87), and frequently compared their notes from class with those from textbooks they had at home (Mean=2.63, SD=0.99).

According to these findings, the participants had positive opinions of their own study habits, particularly with regard to taking notes. The average scores across the board, which tend to be higher on the scale, show a steady and favorable assessment. Individual variations in note-taking practices were reflected in the standard deviations, which indicated a degree of diversity in replies.

The implications of these findings revealed the importance of effective note-taking strategies in supporting positive study habits. Educational institutions and educators may consider reinforcing and promoting the habit of notetaking during both individual study sessions and classroom teaching. Encouraging students to compare class notes with textbook notes at home could further enhance their understanding and retention of the material. The positive self-assessment provides valuable insights into the strengths of respondents' study habits related to notetaking. There are times that they don't feel like writing down notes, maybe because of laziness. It is essential for the understudies because it benefits a lot on quizzes, seatwork, and examinations. That is why note-taking has been a necessary procedure in the school setting to upgrade understudies' understanding. Boyle and Forchelli (2014) stated it is necessary for students in center and secondary schools and turns into the essential method for learning content in colleges.

In relation to learning motivation, Table 12 presents the respondents' self-evaluation of their study habits. It covers a range of topics, including asking for assistance when necessary, researching a subject before teaching it in class, attending regularly, missing some classes, using memorization strategies, and making an effort to get better at subjects that are weaker.

Table 12. *Respondents' Assessment of Their Study Habits Relative to Learning Motivation*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. I take the help of anybody if I do not follow anything.	2.68	0.92	Often
2. I study the subject matter at home thoroughly before it is taught in the classroom.	2.53	0.86	Often
3. I attend my classes regularly on time.	3.54	0.75	Always
4. I frequently remain absent from class.	1.88	1.04	Sometimes
5. If a matter is to be learned by heart, I read and memorize it part by part.	3.00	0.88	Often
6. I try to make up my deficiency in the weak subjects to my best.	2.91	0.86	Often
Total Measure	2.76	0.44	Often

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never 2.50-3.49 Often 1.50-2.49 Sometimes 3.50-4.00 Always

On average, respondents reported a positive assessment of their study habits concerning learning motivation, as indicated by the overall mean of 2.76 (SD=0.44). Individually, respondents stated that they frequently ask for clarification when necessary (Mean=2.68, SD=0.92), frequently study material outside of the classroom before it is taught (Mean=2.53, SD=0.86), consistently arrive at class on

time (Mean=3.54, SD=0.75), occasionally miss class (Mean=1.88, SD=1.04), frequently read and memorize material that must be learned by heart (Mean=3.00, SD=0.88), and frequently try to get better in their weaker subjects (Mean=2.91, SD=0.86).

These findings imply that the respondents showed positive self-assessments of their study habits related to learning motivation. The overall mean values, leaning towards the higher end of the scale, indicate a consistent and positive evaluation. The standard deviations suggest a degree of variability in responses, reflecting individual differences in learning motivation habits.

The implications of these findings highlighted the significance of fostering strong learning motivation as a crucial component of effective study habits. Educational institutions and educators may consider reinforcing and promoting strategies such as seeking help when needed, pre-study of subjects, regular attendance, and consistent efforts to improve in weaker subjects. The positive self-assessment provides valuable insights into the strengths of respondents' study habits related to learning motivation. Charity (2017) provided support for this outcome, stating that there are various ways in which student learners are encouraged, particularly with regard to studying and enhancing academic achievement.

Table 13. Respondents' Assessment of Their Study Habits Relative to Memory

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. I try to recall the matter after reading it.	3.29	0.78	Often
2. I cram certain things without understanding.	2.67	0.87	Often
3. I revise the subject matter from time to time.	2.62	0.82	Often
4. After the examination, I realized that I had made some mistakes in the answers I had written, or I had forgotten some important points	3.39	0.79	Often
Total Measure	2.99	0.48	Often

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never 2.50-3.49 Often 1.50-2.49 Sometimes 3.50-4.00 Always

Survey participants' self-evaluations of their study practices with regard to memory are shown in Table 13. These include topics like reading comprehension, memorization of specific facts without understanding, frequent review of the material, and post-examination reflections on errors or overlooked details.

The overall mean of 2.99 (SD=0.48) shows that respondents generally gave their study habits a positive evaluation in terms of memory. Individual respondents stated that they frequently attempted to recall material after reading it (Mean=3.29, SD=0.78), frequently crammed material without fully understanding it (Mean=2.67, SD=0.87), occasionally revised the material (Mean = 2.62, SD=0.82), and frequently realized after the exam that they had given incorrect answers or had overlooked crucial details (Mean=3.39, SD=0.79).

These results suggest that the respondents exhibited positive self-assessments of their study habits related to memory. The overall mean values, leaning towards the higher end of the scale, indicate a consistent and positive evaluation. The standard deviations suggest a degree of variability in responses, reflecting individual differences in memory-related study habits.

The implications of these findings stressed the significance of effective memory strategies as an integral component of successful study habits. Educational institutions and educators may consider reinforcing and promoting strategies such as regular recall, understanding before memorization, consistent subject matter revision, and reflective practices after examinations. The positive self-assessment provides valuable insights into the strengths of respondents' study habits related to memory. Although it was mentioned that students could recall information, depending on the circumstance, these understudies occasionally struggle to recall information. Because of this, it helps us retain crucial knowledge for shorter periods of time and use it succinctly (Nutley & Soderqvist, 2017).

The self-assessments of respondents about their study habits with regard to exams are shown in Table 14. The total mean of 3.03 (SD=0.43) shows that, on average, respondents gave their study habits connected to exams a positive evaluation.

Individually, respondents reported often maintaining their usual sleep patterns during examination days (Mean=2.83, SD=0.98), often reading the the whole question sheet carefully before writing answers (Mean=3.46, SD=0.77), often answering questions in serial order (Mean=3.19, SD=0.82), always reading their notes carefully before examinations (Mean=3.55, SD=0.69), often preparing for examinations using guides/notes accessible in the market (Mean=2.70, SD=1.03), often outlining answers before writing (Mean=2.75, SD=0.91), often feeling tense when the examination first started (Mean=3.14, SD=0.90), often carefully recording examination results (Mean=2.79, SD=0.96), often singling out weak subjects based on examination results (Mean=2.94, SD=0.83), and frequently prone to comparing grades with others after results are declared (Mean=2.89, SD=0.96).

These results depicted that the respondents expressed positive self-assessments of their study habits related to taking examinations. The overall mean values, leaning towards the higher end of the scale, indicate a consistent and positive evaluation. The standard deviations suggest a degree of variability in responses, reflecting individual differences in examination-related study habits.

The implications of these findings underscored the importance of effective examination preparation strategies as a crucial component of successful study habits. Educational institutions and educators may consider reinforcing and promoting strategies such as maintaining regular sleep habits, careful reading of question papers, systematic answering, reliance on personal notes, and managing stress during examinations. The positive self-assessment provides valuable insights into the strengths of respondents' study habits related to taking examinations. Taking examinations is when assessing the extent to which the student gained knowledge from his

study. According to Price (2018), it is a useful technique for estimating the quantity of knowledge they have acquired and quantifying it.

Table 14. *Respondents' Assessment of Their Study Habits Relative to Taking Examinations*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. During examination days also, I sleep as usual in the night.	2.83	0.98	Often
2. Before writing the answers to the questions in the examination, I read very carefully the entire question paper.	3.46	0.77	Often
3. In the examination, I answer the questions in their serial order.	3.19	0.82	Often
4. Before the examination, I read my notes carefully.	3.55	0.69	Always
5. I prepare for the examinations from the guides/notes available in the market.	2.70	1.03	Often
6. I draw an outline of answers of each question, before writing answers to the questions in the examination.	2.75	0.91	Often
7. I feel tense at the beginning of the examination.	3.14	0.90	Often
8. I carefully record my examination results.	2.79	0.96	Often
9. I single out my weak subjects on the strength of my examination results.	2.94	0.83	Often
10. I tend to compare my marks with others after the results are declared.	2.89	0.96	Often
Total Measure	3.03	0.43	Often

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never 2.50-3.49 Often 1.50-2.49 Sometimes 3.50-4.00 Always

A comprehensive overview of the respondents' evaluations of their study habits on a number of different dimensions—budgeting time, physical health, reading comprehension, taking notes, learning motivation, memory, and taking exams—is given in Table 15. According to the Total Measure mean of 2.91 (SD = 0.35), respondents generally gave good evaluations of their study habits across all categories.

Table 15. *Consolidated Findings of the Respondents' Assessment of Their Study Habits*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Budgeting time	3.01	0.54	Often
Physical condition	2.95	0.48	Often
Reading ability	2.79	0.44	Often
Note-taking	2.88	0.71	Often
Learning Motivation	2.76	0.44	Often
Memory	2.99	0.48	Often
Taking examinations	3.03	0.43	Often
Total Measure	2.91	0.35	Often

Note: 1.00-1.49 Never 2.50-3.49 Often 1.50-2.49 Sometimes 3.50-4.00 Always

Individually, respondents reported often engaging in effective time management strategies (Budgeting time: Mean=3.01, SD=0.54), maintaining positive study habits related to their physical condition (Physical condition: Mean=2.95, SD=0.48), exhibiting positive study habits related to reading ability (Reading ability: Mean=2.79, SD=0.44), actively participating in note-taking (Note-taking: Mean=2.88, SD=0.71), demonstrating strong learning motivation (Learning motivation: Mean=2.76, SD=0.44), employing effective memory strategies (Memory: Mean=2.99, SD=0.48), and preparing well for examinations (Taking examinations: Mean=3.03, SD=0.43).

The findings imply that the respondents' opinions of their study habits on a variety of aspects are largely good. The overall mean values, leaning towards the higher end of the scale, indicated a consistent and positive evaluation. The relatively low standard deviation for the Total Measure suggests a degree of consensus among respondents in their overall assessment of study habits.

The implications of these findings highlighted the multifaceted nature of productive study techniques and the importance of considering various dimensions in supporting students' academic success. Educational institutions and educators may leverage the strengths identified in respondents' study habits and further promote strategies that enhance positive habits across all dimensions. The positive self-assessment provides valuable insights into the overall strengths of respondents' study habits and can inform targeted interventions for continuous improvement. These study techniques are a powerful tool that helps pupils succeed in life (Bashir & Mattoo, 2012). Effective reading is a key component of effective learning, according to Palani (2012), and as reading is connected to the entire educational process, developing strong study habits is necessary for academic achievement.

Problem 3: What is the academic performance of the respondents?

Table 16 provides an overview of the academic performance of the respondents, presenting grades, performance categories, frequency, and percentage distribution.

Most of the participants demonstrated excellent academic performance, with 25.3% achieving outstanding grades in the range of 90-100. Additionally, 54.3% of respondents attained very satisfactory grades in the range of 85-89, and 18.7% achieved satisfactory grades in the range of 80-84. A smaller proportion of respondents, 1.7%, received fairly satisfactory grades in the range of 75-79. Notably, none of the respondents fell below the 74-point threshold, indicating that all students had performance levels classified as "Needs

Improvement."

Table 16. *Academic Performance of the Respondents*

Grades	Performance	Frequency	Percentage (%)
90-100	Outstanding	76	25.3
85-89	Very Satisfactory	163	54.3
80-84	Satisfactory	56	18.7
75-79	Fairly Satisfactory	5	1.7
Below-74	Needs Improvement	0	0.0
Total		300	100.0

Note: Mean (SD) = 87.32 (3.43)

Most of the participants demonstrated excellent academic performance, with 25.3% achieving outstanding grades in the range of 90-100. Additionally, 54.3% of respondents attained very satisfactory grades in the range of 85-89, and 18.7% achieved satisfactory grades in the range of 80-84. A smaller proportion of respondents, 1.7%, received fairly satisfactory grades in the range of 75-79. Notably, none of the respondents fell below the 74-point threshold, indicating that all students had performance levels classified as "Needs Improvement."

The overall mean grade for the respondents is 87.32, with a standard deviation of 3.43. This suggests a relatively high average performance level with a moderate degree of variability among the respondents.

These results indicated a generally strong academic performance among the surveyed students. There were no pupils in the "Needs Improvement" category, indicating that the sample's level of competence was high.

The mean grade and standard deviation provide insights into the central tendency and variability of academic performance, reflecting a generally high academic standard with some variation among individual performances. Educational institutions and educators may acknowledge and build upon these positive academic outcomes while also considering strategies to support continuous improvement and address any variability in student performance.

Lawrence's (2014) study looked into the possible correlation between higher secondary school students' academic achievement and their study habits. His investigation showed that the variables included in the study differ significantly from one another. As previously stated, he provided support with respect to his findings from the theory. Apart from the previously stated investigation, Amuda and Ali (2018) ascertained the correlation between the learners' study practices and their scholastic achievements. Even though the study habits of the respondents showed a statistically significant association with their academic achievement, students should still be able to teach and understand these patterns.

Problem 4: Do the social media usage and benefits predict the academic performance of the respondents?

The results are shown in Table 17. Based on respondents' perceived benefits and social media usage, an ordinal logistic regression analysis was conducted to predict respondents' academic achievement.

Table 17. *Ordinal Logistic Regression Analysis of Predicting Academic Performance of the Respondents by their Social Media Usage and benefits*

Predictors	Estimate B	SE	Wald	p-value	Remarks
Performance Index	-0.453	0.243	3.478	0.062	Not significant
Entertainment	0.393	0.257	2.346	0.126	Not significant
Health Influence	-0.517	0.225	5.260*	0.022	Significant
Isolation	-0.547	0.237	5.329*	0.021	Significant
Social Network Connection	-0.114	0.205	0.308	0.579	Not significant
Consuming time index	0.231	0.221	1.094	0.296	Not significant

Note: Threshold [Grades=Outstanding; Grades=Very Satisfactory] *significant at 0.05 level

The findings show that factors such as the performance index, entertainment, social network connection, and spending time index do not significantly influence academic achievement because their p-values are higher than the accepted cutoff point of 0.05. The statistical research indicated that these social media use and benefit aspects do not significantly affect academic achievement.

Conversely, isolation and the impact on one's health stand out as important determinants. Lower academic performance is linked to higher levels of perceived poor health influence and isolation associated with social media use, according to the negative estimates for both health influence (B=-.517, p=.022) and isolation (B=-.547, p=.021). The Wald statistics for health influence (Wald=5.260) and Isolation (Wald=5.329) exceed the critical value, and their p-values are less than 0.05, signifying statistical significance.

These findings underscored the importance of considering the potential negative effects of social media use, particularly regarding health influence and feelings of isolation, in understanding academic performance among the respondents. The statistically significant results for health Influence and isolation emphasize the need for educators and institutions to be mindful of the potential impact of these aspects of social media use on students' academic outcomes. Students' academic performance may be enhanced by strategies that

address health issues and feelings of isolation while encouraging good and balanced social media use. As a result, Kolhar et al. (2021) established that students' actions are readily impacted by social media platforms due to the offensive remarks made to torment their peers. Social media makes it simple to trick or even entice people to engage in immoral behavior.

Problem 5: Do the study habits predict the academic performance of the respondents?

Table 18. *Multiple Regression Analysis of Predicting Academic Performance of the Respondents by their Study Habits*

Predictors	Estimate B	SE	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Budgeting time	1.416	0.417	3.396***	0.001	Significant
Physical condition	1.785	0.496	3.602***	0.000	Significant
Reading ability	0.679	0.552	1.229	0.220	Not significant
Note-taking	-0.263	0.333	-0.789	0.430	Not significant
Learning motivation	-1.288	0.569	-2.265	0.024	Significant
Memory	-0.823	0.479	-1.720	0.086	Not significant
Taking examinations	-0.178	0.545	-0.327	0.744	Not significant

Note: ***significant at 0.01 level

The findings of a multivariate regression analysis that attempted to predict respondents' academic achievement based on several aspects of their study habits are presented in Table 18.

The findings showed that physical health and time management are statistically significant indicators of academic success. The positive estimates for physical condition ($B=1.785$, $p=.000$) and budgeting time ($B=1.416$, $p=.001$) indicated that better academic performance is correlated with higher levels of good physical well-being and efficient time management. The t-values for both predictors (3.396 for budgeting time and 3.602 for physical condition) exceed the critical value, and their p-values are less than 0.01, signifying statistical significance.

However, because their p-values are higher than the standard cutoff of 0.05, the predictors such as reading comprehension, taking notes, memorization, and exam-taking are not statistically significant in predicting academic performance.

With a negative estimate of -1.288, learning motivation is yet another major predictor that stands out. This result suggested that poorer academic performance is linked to higher levels of learning motivation. Learning motivation has a t-value of -2.265, which is higher than the crucial value. Its p-value is less than 0.05, indicating statistical significance.

These findings provide insights into the factors that significantly influence academic performance among the respondents. Effective time management and positive physical well-being are identified as key contributors to higher academic performance. However, the negative correlation that has been shown between academic achievement and learning motivation points to a complicated relationship that may need more research. Educators and institutions can use these findings to develop targeted interventions and support mechanisms that enhance positive factors while addressing potential challenges related to learning motivation. Good study habits, such as completing assignments, participating actively during class, managing time, maintaining attention, and working hard, have been shown to significantly improve students' academic performance, in accordance with the study that Fouche (2017) referenced.

Problem 6: Do study habits mediate the relationship between social media usage and the academic performance of the respondents?

Table 19. *Mediation Analysis of Study Habits (SH) on the Relationship Between Social Media Usage (SMU) and the Academic Performance (AP) of the Respondents*

Effect	Estimate	SE	Z	p-value	% Mediation	Remarks
Mediation Estimates						
Indirect	0.337	0.178	1.889	0.059	40.6	Not significant
Direct	0.493	0.671	0.735	0.462	59.4	Not significant
Total	0.830	0.657	1.264	0.206	100.0	Not significant
Path Estimates						
SMU → SH	0.279	0.066	4.241**	<0.001		Significant
SH → AP	1.206	0.572	2.109*	0.035		Significant
SMU → AP	0.493	0.671	0.735	0.462		Not significant

Note: ***significant at .001 level *significant at .05 level

The results of a mediation analysis that looked at study habits' (SH) probable mediating function in the link between respondents' academic achievement (AP) and social media usage (SMU) are displayed in Table 19. The analysis provides estimates for indirect and direct effects, total effects, and path estimates.

The findings suggested that there is no mediating role for study habits in the association between social media use and academic achievement. With a p-value of 0.059, above the traditional cutoff of 0.05, it is statistically insignificant. The indirect effect, which represents the mediation through study habits, is assessed at 0.337 with a standard error of 0.178. The percentage mediation is 40.6%, but this result is not deemed significant.

With a standard error of 0.671, the estimated value of the direct effect, which represents the association involving social media usage and academic achievement without the intervention of study habits, is 0.493. The direct effect's p-value is 0.462, which suggests that it is not statistically significant.

The overall effect, or the correlation between social media use and academic achievement, is calculated to be 0.830, with a 0.657 standard error. The p-value for the total effect is 0.206, which is not statistically significant.

Path estimates demonstrated how social media usage significantly influences study habits (SMU → SH: Estimate=0.279, p<0.001), and study habits significantly influence academic performance (SH → AP: Estimate=1.206, p=0.035). However, the direct path from social media usage to academic performance (SMU → AP: Estimate = 0.493, p = 0.462) is not statistically significant.

In conclusion, the mediation analysis shows that study habits have no mediating effect on the correlation between respondents' use of social media and their academic achievement. The lack of statistical significance shown in the indirect effect, direct effect, and total effect indicates that study habits do not appear to be a mediating factor in the relationship between social media usage and academic achievement in this specific research.

Azizi et al. (2019) found a link between a student's academic success and their reliance on social networking. Social media has the benefit of encouraging students to use technology for networking by facilitating contact among them (Roblyer et al., 2010). Madge et al. (2009) provided evidence in favor of the assertion that social media facilitates student interaction and serves as a useful teaching aid. Another advantage is that social media may help close the communication gap between teachers, students, and instructors (Chawinga, 2017). In the modern world, students use a variety of social media platforms for a variety of objectives, particularly in higher education.

Problem 7: What action plan can be formulated based on the findings of the study?

Action Plan: Enhancing Academic Performance Through Social Media Awareness and Study Habit Improvement

Rationale

With an emphasis on time management, social media usage, study habits, learning motivation, and creating a framework for ongoing assessment and modification, the suggested action plan aims to address major issues impacting students' academic achievement. The objective of enhancing time management skills aims to equip students with effective organizational tools and strategies, recognizing the crucial role of efficient time utilization in academic success. Promoting healthy social media use acknowledges the potential impact of online activities on academic performance and seeks to create awareness and responsible engagement. Strengthening study habits and enhancing learning motivation involves targeted interventions to empower students with effective learning strategies and foster a constructive outlook on education. The systematic evaluation and adjustment component ensures that the action plan remains dynamic, responsive to feedback, and adaptable to evolving student needs, thereby fostering a holistic and sustainable approach to improving academic outcomes.

Objective	Strategies	Activities	Time Frame	Resources Needed	Responsible Persons
Improve Time Management Skills	Implement workshops and training sessions.	Conduct time management workshops at the beginning of each semester. Provide resources, such as planners and apps, to help students organize their schedules.	Initiate in the first month of each semester.	Workshop materials, planners, scheduling apps	Academic Support Coordinator
Promote Healthy Social Media Use	Develop awareness campaigns.	Organize awareness sessions during orientation programs. Create and distribute informational pamphlets highlighting the link between social media use and academic performance.	Launch at the beginning of the academic year.	Design and print informational materials.	Student Affairs Office
Strengthen Study Habits	Introduce study habit enhancement programs.	Establish study groups and peer mentoring programs. Provide access to online resources for improving study habits.	Ongoing throughout the academic year	Study materials, online resources, designated study spaces.	Study Support Coordinator
Enhance Learning Motivation	Implement motivational programs.	Organize motivational talks and seminars.	Incorporate into regular academic events.	Guest speakers, certificates of achievement, event	Motivational Programs Coordinator

coordination

Evaluate and Adjust the Action Plan	Establish a system for continuous evaluation and adjustment based on feedback and ongoing assessment.	Recognize and celebrate academic achievements. Collect feedback from students through surveys and focus groups. Analyze academic performance trends and adjust strategies accordingly.	Conduct evaluations at the end of each semester.	Evaluation tools, analysis software	Institutional Research and Evaluation Team
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Conclusion

Based on the analysis and findings of the study, the following conclusions were formulated: This study concluded that respondents exhibited varied perspectives on social media use, sharing a common belief in its potential negative impact on academic performance. Across different dimensions—performance index, entertainment, health influence, isolation, social network connection, and consuming time index—respondents displayed a diverse understanding of social media's role. The total measure, amalgamating these dimensions, indicated a moderate overall agreement, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions to address diverse perceptions and effects.

Analysis of respondents' study habits revealed an overall positive self-assessment, with effective time management, positive physical well-being, and engagement in active study practices. These results collectively indicated a generally favorable evaluation of study habits, providing a foundation for effective academic performance. Additionally, respondents' academic performance showcased commendable achievements, with a majority attaining outstanding and very satisfactory grades. The absence of respondents falling below satisfactory levels underscored a robust academic performance among the surveyed students.

In exploring predictors of academic performance through ordinal logistic regression, certain dimensions of social media use, such as the performance index, entertainment, social network connection, and consuming time index, did not significantly predict academic outcomes. However, health influence and isolation emerged as noteworthy predictors, emphasizing the intricate relationship between perceived health impacts, social isolation, and academic performance.

The multiple regression analysis reinforced these findings, highlighting the significance of effective time management and physical well-being in predicting academic success. However, dimensions like reading ability, note-taking, memory, and taking examinations did not demonstrate statistical significance. Learning motivation, paradoxically, emerged as a significant predictor, suggesting a complex relationship between motivation and academic outcomes.

Then, the study concluded that study habits may not play a mediating role in the relationship between social media use and academic performance. These multifaceted findings underscored the complexity of factors influencing academic success, urging educational institutions to adopt holistic approaches in supporting students' well-being and learning strategies in the digital age.

Based on the findings and conclusions formulated, the following recommendations were set forth: For school administrators, it is recommended to implement awareness programs and workshops addressing the potential impact of social media on academic performance. Incorporating digital literacy into the curriculum can empower students to navigate social media responsibly. Additionally, creating designated spaces for focused study, free from digital distractions, can enhance the learning environment. Collaborative efforts with parents and teachers to monitor students' screen time and provide guidance on healthy social media use would contribute to a more supportive educational atmosphere.

Students should proactively manage their social media use by setting realistic time limits and establishing designated study periods. Developing effective study habits, such as creating a conducive study environment and utilizing time management strategies, can positively impact academic performance. Seeking guidance from teachers or academic counselors on maintaining a healthy balance between social media engagement and study commitments is advisable. Embracing digital well-being tools to monitor and regulate screen time can contribute to a more mindful approach to social media use.

Parents play a crucial role in fostering a balanced digital lifestyle for their children. Encouraging open communication about the challenges and benefits of social media can help parents guide their children effectively. Establishing clear guidelines on screen time, especially during study hours, and modeling healthy digital behavior at home can positively influence students. Parental involvement in school initiatives related to digital literacy and responsible social media use is also recommended.

Teachers should integrate digital literacy modules into the curriculum to equip students with the skills to critically evaluate and responsibly use social media. Implementing periodic check-ins or discussions on the challenges students face in managing their digital lives can provide valuable insights. Teachers can collaborate with school counselors to identify students who may need additional support in managing their online and offline activities.

For future researchers, it is recommended to delve deeper into the specific dynamics of social media use and its impact on academic performance. Exploring nuances related to content consumption, types of social media platforms, and the role of individual personality traits can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding. Additionally, researching effective interventions and strategies for mitigating the potential negative effects of social media on academic performance would be valuable for educational institutions and policymakers.

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